

**КОСМЕТИКА САНОАТИДА ИЖТИМОЙ МЕДИА МАРКЕТИНГИНИНГ
ИСТЕЪМОЛЧИ ҲАРАКАТИГА ТАЪСИРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ**

**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ МАРКЕТИНГА В СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЯХ НА
ПОВЕДЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ В КОСМЕТИЧЕСКОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ**

**EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON
CONSUMER BEHAVIOR: FOCUS ON THE COSMETICS INDUSTRY**

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Аннотация

Ушбу тадқиқотда Ўзбекистондаги косметика саноатида ижтимоий медиа маркетингининг истеъмолчилар харид қилишига таъсирини ўрганишга эътибор қаратдик.

Сўровнома таҳлилий натижаларига кўра, ўйин-кулги ва ҳар бир индивидуал шахсга мослаштириш медиа контенти маълумотини қабул қилиш ва мазкур контентни осон тушунишга ижобий таъсир кўрсатади, янги тренд эса салбий таъсир кўрсатади. Бундан ташқари, ижтимоий медиадан кўп фойдаланиш (тажриба) ва брендга бўлган яқинлик медиа контенти маълумотини қабул қилиш ва контентни осон тушунишга ижобий таъсир кўрсатади, жозибadorлик даражаси эса катта таъсир кўрсатмайди. Шу билан бир қаторда, медиа контенти маълумотини қабул қилиш ва контентни осон тушуниш бренд жозибadorлигига сезиларли ҳисса қўшиб, истеъмолчиларнинг косметик маҳсулот сотиб олиш ниятига ижобий таъсир қилади.

Тадқиқот натижаси шуни кўрсатадики, косметик маҳсулотлар ишлаб чиқарувчи ва сотувчи корхоналар харидорларнинг маҳсулот ҳақидаги маълумотларни осон қабул қилишлари учун ижтимоий медиа унсурларидан тўғри фойдалансагина, харидорларнинг бренд билан алоқаси яхшиланади ва уларнинг харид қилиш нияти ошади.

Калит сўзлар: *Ижтимоий медиа маркетинг фаолияти, маълумотларни қабул қилиш, бренд билан боғланиш, харид қилиш нияти, таъсир этувчилар.*

Аннотация

В этом исследовании мы сосредоточились на изучении влияния маркетинга в социальных сетях на потребительские покупки в косметической промышленности в Узбекистане.

Согласно результатам анализа опроса, развлечения и персонализация положительно влияют на восприятие информации медиаконтента и легкость понимания этого контента, тогда как новый тренд оказывает отрицательное влияние. Кроме того, высокий уровень использования социальных сетей (опыт) и близость к бренду положительно влияют на усвоение информации медиаконтентом и легкость понимания контента, в то время как уровень привлекательности не оказывает существенного влияния. С другой стороны, принятие информации в средствах массовой информации и простота понимания контента в значительной степени способствуют привлекательности бренда и положительно влияют на намерение потребителей покупать косметические продукты.

Результат исследования показывает, что только когда компании, производящие и продающие косметическую продукцию, используют элементы социальных сетей, чтобы облегчить клиентам

получение информации о продукте, отношения клиентов с брендом улучшатся, а их намерение совершить покупку увеличится.

Ключевые слова: Маркетинговая деятельность в социальных сетях, принятие информации, взаимодействие с брендом, намерение совершить покупку, влиятельные лица.

Abstract

In this study, we focused on the relationship between social media marketing and consumer behavior within the cosmetics industry in Uzbekistan. Utilizing survey analysis, we explored the impact of social media on consumer behavior.

Upon analyzing the research findings, we observed that entertainment and customization positively influence information acceptance and content flow, while trendiness has a negative impact. Furthermore, expertise and intimacy positively affect information acceptance and content flow, while attractiveness does not have a discernible effect. Information acceptance and content flow significantly contribute to brand engagement, positively influencing purchase intention.

The study suggests that brands can leverage social media influencers to enhance information acceptance and content flow, ultimately fostering more significant engagement with the brand and an increased intention to purchase.

Keywords: *Social media marketing activities, information acceptance, content flow, brand engagement, purchase intention, influencers.*

Introduction

Cosmetic products sold through digital channels are typically categorized into personal care items such as shampoos, shower gels, makeup, feminine hygiene products, and fragrances; household care items like detergents, brooms, cleaning cloths, and sponges; and health care products including supplements, nutrition, and pharmaceuticals. According to the report [1] on online trading in Uzbekistan, the share of online cosmetics sales is currently at 2%, with a value of \$5 million. However, Uzbekistan's e-commerce market has been steadily growing, with a penetration rate of 2.2% in 2022, up from 0.6% in 2018 [2].

The retail market in Uzbekistan reached an estimated \$414 billion in December 2022 and is projected to reach \$19.6 billion by the end of 2027 [3]. According to TradeGov Report [4], the country's e-commerce generated \$481.3 million in revenue in 2020, representing 68% of total digital revenues, with digital media, e-services, and e-travel making up the remaining 32%. In 2020, Uzbekistan's digital spending was relatively low, accounting for 1.2% of consumer spending per capita, compared to the 3.1% Asian average. E-commerce revenue is forecasted to grow at an annual rate of 6.3% by 2025. The top categories for online purchases were clothing (32%), electronics (31%), food and personal care (14%), toys, hobbies, and DIY products (11.5%), and furniture and appliances (11%).

The cosmetics industry heavily relies on in-person shopping, as consumers often need to test products before purchasing. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, in-person shopping has declined significantly, leading to a sustained drop in sales. In 2023, Uzbekistan's cosmetics market

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[2] Euromonitor (2022). *Analysis on e-commerce in Uzbekistan*. Report.

[3] KPMG. (2023). *Global economic outlook - KPMG. E-commerce in Uzbekistan*.

[4] International Trade Administration (2021). *Uzbekistan - e-commerce*. Report.

generated \$108.60 million in revenue, with an expected annual growth rate of 6.53% from 2023 to 2028. Each person in Uzbekistan contributes approximately \$3.09 to the cosmetics sector [5]. Moreover, an interesting trend is emerging, with non-luxury products expected to represent 80% of sales in the Uzbekistani cosmetics market by 2023. This suggests a consumer preference for more affordable cosmetic options. Additionally, the market is experiencing significant change due to the increasing demand for natural and organic products. This shift can be attributed to a growing consumer interest in sustainable and environmentally friendly beauty products. As a result, Uzbekistan's cosmetics industry is displaying signs of growth, emphasizing affordability and non-luxury products, as well as a strong preference for natural and organic beauty solutions that align with global sustainability trends.

The influence of social media on consumer behavior and its role in communication and product promotion has surged in recent years. According to the 'Digital in 2022' report [6], there are approximately 4.62 billion social media users worldwide, constituting 58.4% of the global population. The international social media user base has grown by more than 10% in the past year, with 424 million new users joining in 2021 alone. East Asia leads in user numbers, boasting 1.158 billion users, while North America has the highest utilization rate at 70%.

The evolution of social interaction and communication through digital platforms has transformed information transfer, with users becoming active producers and facilitating the seamless sharing of ideas. The global marketing landscape reveals a strong inclination towards leveraging YouTube as a video advertising platform. The report "The State of Video Marketing 2021"⁷ underscores the dominance and preference for video-based content in global marketing strategies. The increasing significance of video in overall marketing strategies is highlighted, with 92% of marketers utilizing video, considering it a crucial component of their plans. Social media platforms play a significant role in driving sales in the cosmetics industry, with Instagram and Pinterest leading the way in encouraging cosmetic sales. Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok also contribute to consumer preferences and purchasing decisions in cosmetics. In today's competitive business environment, social media plays a vital role, with video content significantly influencing company management and marketing strategy. The ascendancy of mobile internet media has resulted in a decline in interest in traditional media channels. Social media offers valuable insights into target audiences, facilitating well-informed business decision-making. Social media has emerged as a potent marketing tool in the cosmetics industry, allowing real-time information sharing and fostering connections with consumers. Many empirical studies have yet to examine the influence of social media on the cosmetics industry in Uzbekistan.

[5] Statista. (2023). *Cosmetics - Uzbekistan: Statista market forecast*. Statista.

[6] We Are Social. (2022, January 26). *Digital 2022: Another Year of Bumper Growth*. We Are Social, UK.

[7] Wyzowl. *State of Video Marketing 2021*.

Literature review

The emergence of social media has significantly transformed business practices, particularly in the marketing realm. Companies now employ active Internet marketing strategies to provide users with immersive experiences of their preferred products and brands. Social media is a crucial channel and opportunity for connecting with consumers [8]. Social media enables companies to engage with customers and influence their purchasing decisions, particularly in the cosmetics industry [9]. To develop effective marketing strategies that drive sales, cosmetics companies must understand the impact of product advertisements on social media. Social media has become a significant communication tool in the last ten years. New platforms like YouTube and Instagram have emerged, showing an ongoing trend [10]. The widespread use of electronic devices, especially smartphones and tablet PCs, has expanded social media. Social media is characterized by participation, conversation, sharing, and connection, making it an interactive platform. People interested in specific topics can actively exchange opinions and knowledge, contributing to its dynamic and accessible nature [11].

Previous studies on social media marketing primarily examined the impact of these efforts on consumers' purchasing intentions. For instance, Kim and Ahn [12] delved into how individuals engage with social media, specifically focusing on K-pop content creators who actively produce and share videos on YouTube based on their personal preferences. More recently, there has been a shift in consumer behavior towards personal broadcasting of social media video content. This category encompasses gaming, food, and beauty, with food-related content primarily centered on cooking and dining out. In their research, Chang and Jung [13] discovered that YouTube content spans many user-preferred genres, including cooking, parody, gaming, experiments, reactions, informational videos, hidden cameras, horror experiences, animation, music, beauty and cosmetics, dancing, and entertainment. The quality and persuasiveness of arguments in ads and the quality of information presented on social media significantly influence how people perceive and utilize the information [14].

In recent years, there has been significant enthusiasm about the pivotal role of social media as

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[13] Chang, Y.I., Jung, Y.S. (2019, April 30). A Study on YouTube Product Review Channel Subscribers' Product Attitude Formation Process. *The e-Business Studies*. Global e-Business Association.

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a virtual platform for engaging with customers [15]. This groundbreaking development has motivated marketers to foster meaningful interactions with customers and convey value propositions effectively through this medium [16]. Kim and Ko [17] analyzed the challenges that luxury fashion brands encounter and how they can be addressed through social media marketing to impact customer relationships and purchase intentions. As a marketing tool, social media enables the seamless exchange of information and ideas, enhancing brand value [18]. Given the increasing significance of social media marketing, it is crucial to examine the impact of Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMA) on consumer responses [18]. Godey et al. [19] found that SMMA, such as entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and word of mouth, positively influences brand equity, including brand awareness and brand image. Seo and Park [20] highlighted the extensive influence of SMMA on brand engagement, including brand awareness, brand image, commitment, and e-WOM.

Research on social media marketing has utilized various metrics to assess its effectiveness. For instance, Kim and Ko [18] focused on trendiness, electronic word-of-mouth, customization, entertainment, and interactivity. At the same time, Seo and Park [20] used trendiness, perceived risk, entertainment, interaction, and customization to measure the success of social media marketing. Moreover, the impact of influencers has led retail companies to use influencer marketing more. They host events for influencer brands and create dedicated influencer editorial shops in department stores [21].

Followers connect with influencers over time by engaging with content that matches their interests on social media. When a familiar influencer endorses a product, it can have a word-of-mouth effect similar to recommendations from friends or family members. In the fashion and beauty industries, influencers expand their impact by becoming brand ambassadors, establishing their brands, and releasing products through collaborations [22].

Despite the attention it has received in the literature, studies examining the influence of social

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media marketing on purchase decisions are relatively scarce. Existing research has focused on direct effects on consumer behavior, with limited exploration of potential pathways through which social media marketing elements impact purchase decisions.

Methodology

This study examines the purchasing behavior of Uzbek users who buy cosmetics online or through social media platforms. We used a survey to understand how influencer characteristics, social media marketing activity (SMMA) characteristics, information acceptance, content flow, brand engagement, and product purchase intention are related. The primary survey, offline and online over 45 days from September 4 to October 18, 2023, aimed to gather a diverse and representative sample. We strongly emphasized transparency and ethical considerations, obtaining informed consent from all participants by clearly outlining the study's objectives and ensuring confidentiality. The survey questions are crafted based on the research of Kim [23] to create the questionnaire. The main factors in the questionnaire include SMMA, influencer impact, brand engagement, and purchase intention. Respondents are asked to rate their responses on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "definitely not at all" (1) to "definitely so" (5).

The research encompasses 281 cosmetics users to investigate how social network components influence consumer behavior and the cosmetics industry in Uzbekistan. Data is collected through an online survey questionnaire. Confirmatory factor analysis and Cronbach's α coefficient were used to confirm the reliability of the results using SPSS 23. We assessed the model fit and validity using conceptual reliability and mean-variance extraction values. Finally, we conducted path analysis to confirm the research hypothesis using AMOS 20.

Analysis and results

Two of the initial 281 participants were excluded because they did not use social media platforms, resulting in a dataset of 279 individuals for descriptive analysis. A significant disparity was observed in cosmetics consumption, with one-third (33.3%) of participants reporting no cosmetic purchases, while a substantial two-thirds (66.7%) had made cosmetic acquisitions. The gender distribution revealed a predominant female presence, with 71.7% (200 participants) female respondents and 28.3% (79 participants) male respondents. The age distribution highlighted a concentration of participants in the younger demographic, with 39.4% falling within the 18 to 22 age range. Those aged 23 to 27 represented 18.3%, and the 28 to 32 age range accounted for 16.5% of the respondents.

Occupationally, 46.2% identified as students, emphasizing the youth-centric nature of the sample.

[23] Kim, K.Y. (2020). Domestic Online Video Platform: OTT Development Study. Doctoral dissertation, Soonchunhyang University.

Meanwhile, 31.5% of participants were engaged in educational pursuits. Lifestyle preferences indicated a significant inclination towards healthy (31.9%), active (30.5%), and work-related (14%) lifestyles.

Regarding income distribution, most participants (39.4%) reported an income below 2.5 million UZS, followed by 24.4% earning between 2.5 and 5 million UZS. Participants earning more than 10 million UZS constituted 16.5%, while those falling within the income brackets of 5 to 7.5 million UZS and 7.5 to 10 million UZS accounted for 11.8% and 7.9%, respectively.

This research utilized a carefully designed questionnaire consisting of 41 varied items as the primary tool for data collection. Table 1 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the questionnaire items for each aspect, including SMMA, Influencer Characteristics, Information Acceptance, Content Flow, Brand Engagement, and Purchase Intention. These six aspects were central to the study, providing detailed insights into the interplay of social media, influencers, information processing, and consumer behaviors.

Table 1. Variables and their sources

Variables		Number of Items	Sources
SMMA characteristics	Entertainment	3	Seo and Park (2017) Kim and Ko (2012)
	Trendiness	3	
	Customization	3	
Influencer`s characteristics	Attractiveness	3	Kwak and Yoh (2021)
	Expertise	3	
	Intimacy	3	
Information acceptance		8	Weman (2011); Gummerus, et al. (2012)
Content Flow		3	Kwak and Yoh (2021)
Brand Engagement		5	Park et.al (2019) Aaker (2001) Seo and Park (2018)
Purchase Intention		7	Kwak and Yoh (2021) Aji et al (2020) McKnight and Chervany (2002); Wang and Chang (2013), Yoo and Donthu (2001)
Moderator			Gender, Age, Occupation, Lifestyle, Income

Source: Reorganized based on Ji, H.K., Eunah, Y. (2020), Tenzin Ch., and Lee Y.Ch. (2020)

Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted in two steps to evaluate the measurement model. The results indicated that all model fit indices were within acceptable limits ($\chi^2/df=2.08$, $TLI=0.89$, $CFI=0.91$, and $RMSEA=0.062$). Although the χ^2 value was significant ($\chi^2=1527.722$ ($df=734$, $p=0.000$)), it still reflected a reasonable model fit (≤ 3). The model's internal consistency was further assessed using factor loadings and t-values. The construct indicators loaded exclusively on their specified constructs without any cross-loadings. All t-values exceeded the benchmark of 1.96, with the lowest t-value being 9.157.

Cronbach's alpha is a valuable measure used to assess the reliability of a scale or a set of survey items,

offering insights into the consistency of responses across items. The resulting Cronbach's reliability coefficients are as follows: Entertainment (0.735), Customization (0.748), Attractiveness (0.794), Trendiness (0.803), Intimacy (0.851), Expertise (0.856), Content flow (0.893), Brand engagement (0.896), Information acceptance (0.923), and Purchase intention (0.918). These coefficients comfortably exceeded the standard threshold of 0.60, meeting the baseline of 0.7 for moderate reliability.

Table 2. Internal Consistency, Composite, and Convergent Validity Results

Variables	λ	λ^2	$1-(\lambda^2)$	CR	AVE	
Entertainment	SMM_1_1	0,71	0,50	0,50	0,75	0,50
	SMM_1_2	0,77	0,59	0,41		
	SMM_1_3	0,63	0,40	0,60		
Trendiness	SMM_2_1	0,73	0,53	0,47	0,81	0,58
	SMM_2_2	0,75	0,57	0,43		
	SMM_2_3	0,80	0,64	0,36		
Customization	SMM_3_1	0,63	0,40	0,60	0,76	0,51
	SMM_3_2	0,69	0,47	0,53		
	SMM_3_3	0,82	0,67	0,33		
Attractiveness	INF_1_1	0,70	0,50	0,50	0,80	0,57
	INF_1_2	0,74	0,54	0,46		
	INF_1_3	0,82	0,67	0,33		
Expertise	INF_2_1	0,80	0,63	0,37	0,86	0,67
	INF_2_2	0,86	0,74	0,26		
	INF_2_3	0,80	0,64	0,36		
Intimacy	INF_3_1	0,79	0,62	0,38	0,85	0,66
	INF_3_2	0,86	0,74	0,26		
	INF_3_3	0,79	0,62	0,38		
Information acceptance	ACC_1	0,77	0,60	0,40	0,92	0,60
	ACC_2	0,84	0,70	0,30		
	ACC_3	0,79	0,63	0,37		
	ACC_4	0,81	0,66	0,34		
	ACC_5	0,65	0,42	0,58		
	ACC_6	0,80	0,64	0,36		
	ACC_7	0,76	0,58	0,42		
	ACC_8	0,76	0,57	0,43		
Content flow	CFL_1	0,87	0,75	0,25	0,89	0,74
	CFL_2	0,86	0,74	0,26		
	CFL_3	0,85	0,73	0,27		
Brand engagement	BRE_1	0,72	0,51	0,49	0,90	0,64
	BRE_2	0,84	0,70	0,30		
	BRE_3	0,80	0,64	0,36		
	BRE_4	0,80	0,65	0,35		
	BRE_5	0,82	0,68	0,32		
Purchase intention	PI_1	0,81	0,66	0,34	0,92	0,62
	PI_2	0,78	0,61	0,39		
	PI_3	0,79	0,63	0,37		
	PI_4	0,78	0,61	0,39		
	PI_5	0,72	0,51	0,49		
	PI_6	0,77	0,60	0,40		
	PI_7	0,83	0,69	0,31		

The Composite Reliability (CR) values were strong (Table 2), all exceeding 0.7 for the following constructs: Entertainment (0.75), Customization (0.76), Attractiveness (0.80), Trendiness (0.81), Intimacy (0.85), Expertise (0.86), Content flow (0.89), Brand engagement (0.90), Information acceptance (0.92), and Purchase intention (0.92). These results confirm the overall reliability of our measurement model. Moreover, all

constructs have Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values comfortably exceeding 0.50, solidifying our model's capability to explain more than half of the variance in its indicators.

The Collinearity statistics indicate no significant multicollinearity among the study variables. The Tolerance values range from 0.187 to 0.504, and the corresponding VIF values range from 1.986 to 5.349, suggesting an acceptable level of independence among the independent variables.

Table 3. Collinearity statistics

Variables	Tolerance	VIF
Entertainment	.444	2.253
Trendiness	.443	2.258
Customization	.504	1.986
Attractiveness	.428	2.338
Expertise	.303	3.302
Intimacy	.297	3.368
Information acceptance	.187	5.349
Content flow	.240	4.159
Brand engagement	.213	4.685

Dependent variable: Purchase intension

H1-1: Entertainment positively and significantly affects information acceptance.

H1-2: Trendiness positively and significantly affects information acceptance.

H1-3: Customization positively and significantly affects information acceptance.

These hypotheses investigated the potential impact of various social media marketing activities (SMMA) on consumers' willingness to accept information. The study hypothesized that the features of SMMA, such as the entertainment value, trendiness, and availability of customization, would positively predict information acceptance. A multiple regression analysis was conducted to test this hypothesis. The results revealed that 31.9% of the variation in information acceptance could be explained by the three independent variables collectively, $F(3,274) = 44.215, p < .001$. Upon examining the unique contributions of the independent variables, it was found that the entertainment value of SMM activities ($\beta = 0.497, t = 6.702, p < .001$) and the customization of SMM activities ($\beta = 0.248, t = 3.561, p < .001$) positively predicted information acceptance. However, the trendiness of the activities ($\beta = -0.161, t = 2.124, p = .035$) had a negative impact on information acceptance.

H2-1: Entertainment positively and significantly affects content flow.

H2-2: Trendiness positively and significantly affects content flow.

H2-3: Customization positively and significantly affects content flow.

The hypothesis proposed a positive correlation between SMMA characteristics and content flow. After

conducting multiple regression analysis, the findings indicated that the model explained 26.1% of the variance in Information acceptance, and the combined influence of the three independent variables was statistically significant ($F(3,275) = 33.689, p < .001$). Content flow was positively influenced by entertainment in SMMA ($\beta=0.392, t=5.085, p < .001$) and customization of SMMA ($\beta=0.305, t=4.216, p<.001$). However, the trendiness of SMMA activities had a negative impact on content flow ($\beta=-0.166, t=-2.110, p=.036$).

H3-1: Attractiveness positively and significantly affects information acceptance.

H3-2: Expertise positively and significantly affects information acceptance.

H3-3: Intimacy positively and significantly affects information acceptance.

The hypothesis suggested that specific influencer characteristics would positively impact content flow. To test this, we used multiple regression analysis, which revealed that the three independent variables could explain 51.0% of the variance in information acceptance. The combined effect was highly significant ($F(3,274) = 96.950, p < .001$). When examining the unique contributions of the independent variables, the results indicated that the professionalism (expertise) of influencers ($\beta=0.339, t=4.101, p<.001$) and the closeness (intimacy) to influencers ($\beta=0.351, t=4.452, p<.001$) both positively predicted information acceptance. However, the attractiveness of influencers ($\beta=0.073, t=1.148, p=.252$) did not significantly influence information sharing.

H4-1: Attractiveness positively and significantly affects content flow.

H4-2: Expertise positively and significantly affects content flow.

H4-3: Intimacy positively and significantly affects content flow.

The hypothesis suggested a positive relationship between influencer traits and content engagement. Through multiple regression analysis, the findings indicated that the model explained 59.6% of the variability in Information acceptance, and the combined impact of the three independent variables was statistically significant ($F(3,275) = 137.571, p<.001$). The expertise of influencers was found to be a positive predictor of content engagement ($\beta=0.309, t=4.123, p<.001$), and intimacy with influencers was positively correlated with content engagement ($\beta=0.427, t=5.970, p<.001$). However, influencers' attractiveness did not significantly affect content engagement ($\beta=0.090, t=1.556, p=.121$). In summary, individuals are more likely to value influencers' expertise and feel close to them. However, the attractiveness of influencers may not significantly affect individuals' willingness to share social media content and engage with their posts.

H5: Information acceptance positively and significantly affects brand engagement.

H6: Content flow positively and significantly affects brand engagement.

The study hypothesized that information sharing and media content positively affect brand engagement. The results of the multiple regression analysis indicated that 72.7% of the variance in brand engagement could be explained by these two independent variables collectively, with a significant F value ($F(2,275) = 370.117, p < .001$). Upon closer examination of the individual contributions of the independent variables, it was found that both information-sharing activities ($\beta=0.547, t=10.284, p < .001$) and content flow ($\beta=0.348, t=6.542, p < .001$)

had a positive predictive effect on brand engagement.

H7: Brand engagement positively and significantly affects purchase intention.

It was hypothesized that the level of engagement with a brand would positively affect purchase intention. The results of the multiple regression analysis indicate that 65.2% of the variability in purchase intention can be explained by individuals' engagement with cosmetic brands, with a significant $F(1,277) = 520.908, p < .001$. This suggests that brand engagement ($\beta = 0.808, t = 22.823, p < .001$) significantly and positively influences purchase intention.

Figure 1. Visualization of the model.

Conclusion and recommendations

Several findings are consistent with previous research, confirming the validity of established concepts. The positive impact of Entertainment and Customization on Information acceptance reflects the findings [24], which emphasized the importance of engaging and trendy content in boosting brand engagement. Similarly, the influence of Expertise and Intimacy on Information acceptance aligns with the conclusions [25], underscoring the significance of brand-consumer relationships in shaping perceptions.

The strong connections identified between Information acceptance and the following stages, Brand engagement and Purchase intention, support the theoretical framework [18]. This is consistent with the idea that a well-informed and engaged consumer is more inclined to form a positive brand relationship, ultimately increasing the probability of purchasing.

The absence of emphasis on trendiness and attractiveness in shaping content flow contradicts

[24] Cheung, M.L., Pires, G., Rosenberger, P.J. (2020). The influence of perceived social media marketing elements on consumer-brand engagement and brand knowledge. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 32(3), 695–720.
 [25] Helal, G., Ozuem, W. (2019). Social Media and Social Identity in the millennial generation. *Leveraging Computer-Mediated Marketing Environments*, 43–82.

the results [26], highlighting the strategic importance of these factors in the cosmetics industry. This difference could be due to the varied nature of the cosmetics sector and the specific circumstances under which the research was carried out.

Table 4. Hypothesis results

Hypothesis	Standardized coefficient	t-value	Result
Entertainment → Information acceptance (H1-1)	0.594	6.702***	Supported
Trendiness → Information acceptance (H1-2)	-0.211	-2.124*	Not supported
Customization → Information acceptance (H1-3)	0.326	3.561***	Supported
Attractiveness → Information acceptance (H2-1)	0.089	1.148	Not supported
Expertise → Information acceptance (H2-2)	0.402	4.101***	Support
Intimacy → Information acceptance (H2-3)	0.408	4.452***	Support
Entertainment → Content flow (H3-1)	,464	5.085***	Supported
Trendiness → Content flow (H3-2)	-0.215	-2.110*	Not supported
Customization → Content flow (H3-3)	0.396	4.216***	Supported
Attractiveness → Content flow (H4-1)	0.108	1.382	Not supported
Expertise → Content flow (H4-2)	0.362	4.123***	Support
Intimacy → Content flow (H4-3)	0.490	5.970***	Support
Information acceptance → Brand engagement (H5)	0.489	10.284***	Support
Content flow → Brand engagement (H6)	0.315	6.542***	Support
Brand engagement → Purchase intention (H7)	0.719	22.823***	Support

The findings highlight the importance of Expertise and Intimacy in shaping Content flow. This contrasts with the research [27], which mainly centered on prominent brand elements. It indicates that, within social media, establishing a deeper connection and perceived expertise are crucial factors in content engagement and sharing. Furthermore, it is essential to consider the following recommendations:

1. Companies should prioritize creating content highlighting expertise and fostering a strong audience connection. This involves highlighting your brand's knowledge and authority in the industry and creating personalized and relatable content to build intimacy with the audience.

2. As indicated by the research, companies should highlight the positive impact of entertainment and customization on information acceptance. Integrating interactive and trendy content into a brand's communication strategies can boost brand engagement and information acceptance.

3. Although the study did not find a significant influence on trendiness and attractiveness, it is crucial to stay updated on evolving consumer preferences and adjust the strategies accordingly.

[26] Kontu, H., Vecchi, A. (2016). Fashion and social media. Handbook of Research on Global Fashion Management and Merchandising, 649–669.

[27] Han, Y.J., Nunes, J.C., Drèze, X. (2010). Signaling status with luxury goods: The Role of Brand Prominence. Journal of Marketing, 74(4), 15–30.

Companies should continuously monitor trends and consumer behavior to ensure the content remains relevant and appealing.

4. Companies should consider the industry's specific context when assessing the influence of different elements on content flow. Variations in findings about trendiness and attractiveness may be linked to the diverse nature of industries and consumer behaviors within those contexts.

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